

METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The given article presents the ways of developing professional competence of students through the use of modern innovative methods for developing students' professional competence in distance learning. The research works of domestic and foreign scientists on the issues of distance education, on the use of pedagogical technologies in distance education are studied and compared. In order to develop the professional competence of students, recommendations were given on the use of some interactive methods in distance learning, and experimental work was carried out.*

Keywords: *distance education, competence, professional competence, platform, education system, innovative methods, learning process, training, research, development.*

Introduction. It is important to mention that the new concept of education until 2030, adopted by international organizations and developed countries of the world, recognizes that "Education is the main driving force for development and an important activity that ensures the achievement of sustainable development goals". The level of development of technologies and the requirements of the time have determined the rapid introduction of another area of education - distance education. Instead of traditional forms of training, the education system widely uses elements of e-education. Along with the desire of the education system for innovative processes, systematic work is carried out to radically change the educational process in higher education institutions, optimize the management of independent training of students with the help of modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies. Certainly, electronic technologies are used in the educational process, providing high-quality education, development of knowledge, skills, abilities and professional competencies.

It is not a secret that its use in the process of distance education and in the system of continuous education remains the requirement of the time. Modern technologies in education can be conditionally divided into 3 main areas: information technology (information and computer, information and communication); active teaching methods; distance learning (the latter can be considered both as a technology and as an organizational innovation). With a certain degree of conventionality, it is now possible to introduce non-traditional teaching methods using telecommunications and network technologies, as well as active modeling methods.

It is known to everyone that in distance learning, the student and teacher are separated from each other and constantly communicate with each other using specially created training courses, forms of control, electronic communication and other Internet technologies. Distance education based on the use of Internet technologies provides access to the global information and educational network, performs a number of important new functions based on the principle of integration and interaction. In the system of higher education institutions and scientific organizations around the world, scientific research is conducted to improve the methodological support of distance

education subjects, develop the professional competence of students, and widely and publicly use multimedia, information and communication technologies in education.

Literature review. In the book by E. F. Zeer [1] the most complete psychological forms of professional development of the individual in the process of professional self-government in modern socio-economic conditions, the features of the development of professional competence are studied. He evaluates professional competence as one of the main components of the structure of professional activity. This textbook examines the theoretical and methodological foundations of professional development, its metapsychological categories, the features of the formation of the subject of professional activity of students of higher educational institutions studying psychology. Psychological obstacles to the professional development of a person are analyzed.

Moreover, in the book by A.K. Markova [2] for the first time for all readers in a systematic and generalized form the psychological concept of professionalism is presented. When constructing a professionogram, a task-personal approach is manifested. A personal card of professional psychological diagnosis is issued. Psychological factors that help and hinder the professional growth of a specialist are summarized. The book is intended for every working person thinking about the results and prospects of their professional development, especially young people just starting their professional path:

- specialists (psychologists, social workers) providing specific assistance to people in solving problems of professional growth;
- heads of institutions that assess and certify the level of professional skills of employees;
- teachers of vocational educational institutions of various types, studying in courses for admission to specialization;
- researchers studying the problems of professional skills.

Besides that, in the second part of the monograph by E.I. Kudryavtseva [3], the history of the study of competence is considered from the point of view of the importance of this problem in the development of the presented activity of the subject and its effectiveness. Here, attention is paid to the most hotly debated issues related to the use of the idea of competence and the formation of a competence-based approach. Particular attention is paid to such topics as education and competence, and the construction of competence. The concept of "competence" is used to determine the individual characteristics that help a person perform his or her work better, and "competence" is considered a description of the requirements for the work performed.

In the works of M.A. Innazarov, O.A. Vasileva, A.Sh. Galimova, V.B. Gargay, V.D. Ivanov, J.I.V. Kleeva, T.V. Korotovskix, P.A. Korchemny, O.A. Nekrasova, I.E. Savenkova, and Yu.G. Tatur, issues related to the formation of professional competence and the improvement of the role of pedagogical staff in enhancing their qualifications within electronic education are analyzed. Additionally, strategies for developing the professional competence of educators active in educational institutions are discussed, along with innovative approaches to professional competence development and the self-development of educators, as examined by Raven John, Dirk Richter, Adnan Hakim, Michael D. Toth, Mardia Hi. Rahman, Hutmacher Walo, Mareike Kunter, Bjorn Oskarsson, Robert Marzano, Thilo Kleickmann, and others.

According to the author, professional competence is the sum of knowledge, skills and abilities, experience, personal qualities, which are based on existing knowledge and experience in the process of education and socialization, aimed at ensuring independent and successful participation of a person in life.

Since the introduction of distance education, many scientists (S.G. Abdullaev, L.K. Averchenko, Yu.S. Avraamov, V. Andryushin, I.I. Bobrova, O.V. Genne, O.D. Dyachkin and others) have experience in developing methods of computer teaching mathematics, assessing the effectiveness of the distance education system, distance pedagogy in adult education, the practice of forming an information and educational environment based on distance technologies, information technologies in modern education systems, the use of electronic educational complexes as a way of transition to the methodology of distance learning, a new step in the development of the distance education system, conducting scientific work on such topics as distance methods of teaching students computer science and physics.

G.A. Gareeva's work [5] is devoted to the formation of students' information competence in the context of distance education. Distance education technologies allow creating an educational environment for the formation, development and demonstration of competence. The information competence of students studying using electronic technologies is formed through the use of the information and educational environment of distance education.

The conducted analysis proves that although a lot of research has been done on the problem of organizing and improving the educational process in the electronic education system in higher education institutions, the fact that the problem of improvement of the methodology for developing students' professional competence in the context of distance education has not been studied determines the relevance of the research topic.

Main part. Definitely, students need to develop their professional competence and ability to professionally adapt, be able to apply the acquired knowledge in their professional activities and be able to adapt to the requirements of the employer. Professional competence is the acquisition by a specialist of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity, and their practical application at a high level.

Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of individual knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Competence also requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, assimilation of new information, understanding of important social requirements, searching for new information, its processing and the ability to use it in one's work. Let's consider distance education systems that allow improving the methods of developing students' professional competence in distance education.

According to eLearning Industry, the largest consulting agency in the field of online education, there are more than 800 common distance learning systems in the world. We can analyze the distance education system by many criteria, and they are usually subjective. For now, let's divide into two areas:

The best free distance learning platforms:

1. The Moodle platform is developed by users using new modules (more than 1500), so Moodle has wide customization options for the interface and functions.

2. A tutor is developed by its own community on GitHub. Like Moodle, ATutor has fewer ready-made modules, but it has a built-in designer.

Forma LMS. From general analysis of knowledge levels to detailed statistics and reports, Forma LMS has a huge number of available functions. The service also offers various certifications, professional management support, as well as a variety of tools for managing virtual classrooms, including various calendars and event managers.

Spring Learn. The Ispring Learn online training platform is used by private business trainers and large companies with a developed branch network: Alfa Capital, Lamoda, PwC, RTRS, Unilever. This is an Internet service, so there is no need to download the program, install it on the server or configure it. To get started, all you need to do is register on the site, download training materials and assign personnel.

With the transition to e-learning, interactive methods had to be changed and reworked. Lessons are organized in the form of working in pairs and small groups, as well as using role-playing methods, distance education, use of online games and various educational simulators, use of research projects, work with documents and information sources, creative works. Let's look at some interactive learning methods.

1) Brownian motion. Students are divided into groups, and a group leader is appointed to collect information. For example, when the subject of checking functions is repeated in a higher mathematics class, students choose examples and work independently, then discuss in groups, and at the end, each group sends their answers, or they can demonstrate using "Let's View software on online boards" such as Smart Notebook, Miro.

2) Take the position. This method is a good starting point for working with controversial issues and questions. This method is effective for use as an introductory exercise to demonstrate the diversity of opinions on the topic being studied, and to give students the opportunity to express their point of view. In advance, the tiles appear on the virtual board. Additionally, all participants, thinking about the question, point to one of the four tiles. Then there will be an exchange of ideas and debates. Any participant can freely change the position under the influence of reliable evidence. The results are summarized.

3) Blitz survey. This method is effective in any educational format. You can explore the Yandex tutorial site with a screen display and use it remotely.

The use of distance education contributes to the development of student's personality, he sees development in himself, and the teacher sees it, as well. Creates additional opportunities for the development of students.

By summarizing it should be suggested that the level of knowledge of students studying at a distance must meet the requirements of SES and be no lower than that of students studying at a traditional education. Therefore, the organization of distance education with the effective use of modern innovative technologies, educational software, mobile applications, various platforms and not only education, but also upbringing is one of the main tasks of each teacher. In the process of distance education, the method of developing the professional competence of students is also important, and the university is assessed based on the attitude of the student who studied at a distance learning to his work and professional competence, therefore, it can be recognized that this topic is relevant.

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